

Synthesis of some new mixed-ligand complexes of chromium(III) involving quadridentate Schiff bases N,N' -(2-hydroxy)propylenebis{(2-imino-3-oximino)-butane} and N,N' -(2-hydroxy)propylenebis(acetylacetonimine) and bidentate Schiff base N,N' -propylenebis(benzaldimine)

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Some mixed-ligand complexes of chromium(III) have been synthesized by the reactions of different chromium salts with quadridentate Schiff bases N,N' -(2-hydroxy)propylenebis{(2-imino-3-oximino)butane} and N,N' -(2-hydroxy)propylenebis(acetylacetonimine) and a bidentate Schiff base N,N' -propylenebis(benzaldimine) under varied reaction conditions. The stereochemistry of the complexes has been discussed.

In continuation of our earlier study on chromium(III) complexes, we have studied the reactions of N,N' -(2-hydroxy)propylenebis{(2-imino-3-oximino)butane} (abbreviated to H_2L^1) and N,N' -(2-hydroxy)propylenebis(acetylacetonimine) (abbreviated to H_2L^2) derived respectively by the condensation of 1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol with diacetyl-monoxime and acetylacetonimine with different chromium(III) compounds under varied reaction conditions leading to the isolation of many new chromium(III) mixed-ligand complexes. This paper also includes the mixed-ligand complexes of chromium(III) involving N,N' -propylenebis(benzaldimine) (abbreviated to L^3). Chromium(III) complexes of mixed-ligands and macrocycles have multifaceted importance. Despite extensive work on chromium(III) mixed-ligand systems¹, the biologically active form of chromium is yet to be properly defined. To throw more light on the topic we have been carrying out work on the chromium(III) complexes with different types of ligands and in this paper we describe the preparation, properties and characterization of some new chromium(III) mixed-ligand complexes.

Results and Discussion

The reactions of the Schiff bases H_2L^1 , H_2L^2 and L^3 with $CrCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$, $NH_4[Cr(NCS)_4(NH_3)_2] \cdot H_2O$ and $K_3[Cr(NCS)_6] \cdot 4H_2O$ under varied reaction conditions yielded many new mixed-ligand complexes of chromium(III) (1-3 and 5-10). Reaction of L^3 with $CrCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ in the presence of zinc dust (excess) and bipyridine (bipy) generated a cationic heterochelate $[Cr(L^3)_2(bipy)]^{3+}$ which was isolated as its perchlorate salt, $[Cr(L^3)_2(bipy)](ClO_4)_3$ (4). The complexes (Table 1) are all coloured and stable in

air when dried. The elemental analyses of the compounds agree with the formulations. The molecular weights also support these formulations.

The molar conductance data (Table 1) reveal that compounds 1, 2, 8 and 9 are non-electrolytes in DMSO solution. On the other hand, complexes 5, 6 and 10 are 1 : 1 electrolytes in the same solvent. However, complexes 3 and 7 are 1 : 2 electrolytes, while the Λ_M value found for complex 4 may be taken as the 1 : 3 electrolytic nature of the complex in DMSO solution. These values are in conformity with the proposed formulations². The room temperature magnetic moments (3.70–3.85 B.M.) are slightly lower than the spin-only value for a d^3 ion, and this aspect has been discussed thoroughly elsewhere^{3,4}.

The electronic absorption spectra of the chromium(III) complexes 1-10 in solution show three bands (in methanol) at 17000–21000, 20000–23000 and 25000–27000 cm^{-1} . Some of the chelates, when taken in nujol mull, give almost identical spectra, especially in the range 18000–25000 cm^{-1} . This suggests that the environment of chromium(III) is almost the same in solid as well as in solution. The bands observed in the range 18000–25000 cm^{-1} may be considered as the split components of the ${}^4T_{2g}(O_h)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F)(O_h)$ terms despite their high molar extinction coefficients. Similar high extinction coefficients were observed for band in this region in the chromium(III) complexes of N -substituted salicylaldehydes, N,N' -ethylenebis(acetylacetonimine)⁴. If these are at all $d-d$ bands, then the high molar extinction coefficients are possibly due to contributions from ligand transitions. However, according to Yamada *et al.*, the $d-d$ bands in such chelates might appear around 15000 cm^{-1} , which in the

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of some chromium(III) complexes*

Compd.	Mol. wt. Found/(Calcd.)	Analysis % Found/(Calcd.)		Λ_M^a $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		Cl	Cr	
[Cr(L ¹)(Py)Cl].2H ₂ O (1)	460	7.80	11.44	11.8
C ₁₆ H ₂₇ N ₅ O ₃ ClCr	(456.9)	(7.79)	(11.38)	
[Cr(L ²)(Py)Cl].H ₂ O (2)	-	8.22	11.98	12.0
C ₁₈ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₄ ClCr	-	(8.13)	(11.90)	
[Cr(L ³) ₂ (Py)Cl](ClO ₄) ₂ (3)	880	12.33	5.98	85.0
C ₃₉ H ₄₁ N ₅ O ₈ Cl ₃ Cr	(866.26)	(12.29)	(6.00)	
[Cr(L ³) ₂ (bipy)](ClO ₄) ₃ (4)	-	-	5.60	100.8
C ₄₄ H ₄₄ N ₆ O ₁₂ Cl ₃ Cr	-	(10.57)	(5.16)	
[Cr(L ¹)(NH ₃) ₂](SCN) (5)	-	-	13.75	46.00
C ₁₂ H ₂₄ N ₇ O ₃ Cl ₃ SCr	-	-	(13.05)	
Cr(L ²)(NH ₃) ₂ (SCN) (6)	410	-	13.20	38.00
C ₁₄ H ₂₆ N ₅ O ₃ SCr	(396.42)	-	(13.12)	
Cr(L ³) ₂ (NCS)(NH ₃) ₃ (SCN) ₂ (7)	-	-	7.02	82.00
C ₃₇ H ₃₉ N ₈ S ₃ Cr	-	-	(6.99)	
[Cr(HL ¹)(NCS) ₂] (8)	450	-	12.58	20.00
C ₁₃ H ₁₉ N ₆ O ₃ S ₂ Cr	(423.45)	-	(12.27)	
[Cr(HL ²)(NCS) ₂] (9)	458	-	12.80	18.00
C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₄ S ₂ O ₃ Cr	(421.47)	-	(12.34)	
[Cr(L ³) ₂ (NCS) ₂]SCN (10)	-	-	7.27	38.00
C ₃₇ H ₃₆ N ₇ S ₃ Cr	-	-	-	

*All the compounds gave satisfactory analyses for C, H and N.

^a10⁻³M solution in DMSO at room temperature

present case are masked by more intense bands.

The IR spectra of the ligands show medium to strong bands in the region 3200–3300 cm⁻¹ assignable to ν_{OH} (=C(CH₃)OH) in the case of H₂L² and a band at 3000–3400 cm⁻¹ assignable to ν_{OH} (oxime) in the case of ligand H₂L¹. The presence of OH (secondary alcoholic) in these two ligands has been demonstrated by appearance of a band around 3400 cm⁻¹. The broad nature of the bands suggests hydrogen bonding^{6,7}. The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (azomethine) in the ligands H₂L¹, H₂L² and L³ appeared in the range 1610–1620 cm⁻¹ as very strong band. The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (oxime linkage) mode in the free ligand H₂L¹ is possibly submerged by the other strong band at around 1615 cm⁻¹. The $\nu_{\text{N-O}}$ mode for the ligand H₂L¹ was observed as a strong band⁸ at 940 cm⁻¹. The $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ (secondary alcohol) appeared around 1350 cm⁻¹ in the free ligands H₂L¹ and H₂L² and remained unchanged in the metal complexes demonstrating non-involvement of this group in the complexes⁹. Besides, disappearance of bands around 3000–3300 cm⁻¹ suggests deprotonation of oxime OH (of H₂L¹) and alcoholic OH (=C(CH₃)OH of H₂L²) allowing these ligands to function as dibasic quadridentate fashion. However, presence of a broad band

around 3400 cm⁻¹ (secondary alcoholic group) complicates this interpretation. The bands due to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (both azomethine and oxime) shifted to lower frequencies by about 10–25 cm⁻¹ compared to the free ligand values, indicating bonding through N₄ (involving ligand H₂L¹), N₂O₂ (involving ligand H₂L²) and N₂ (involving ligand L³).

The IR spectra of **8** and **9** showed bands around 2070 (s) and 760 cm⁻¹ (m) due to C≡N and C–S stretching vibrations respectively^{6,12}. The bonding of thiocyanato group with chromium(III) ion occurs through nitrogen as evident from the band due to $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ at about 760 cm⁻¹. Based on the data available in literature, it may be concluded that thiocyanato group coordinates through nitrogen for first row transition metals and through sulfur for the second row transition metals. The ionic nature of SCN in complexes **5** and **6** is supported by the appearance of bands around 2045 (CN) and 735 cm⁻¹ (CS). On the other hand, the IR spectra of complexes **7** and **10** showed bands at ~2065 (s) (a doublet) and 755 (m) cm⁻¹ (a doublet) assignable to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$, respectively. The presence of both coordinated and ionic SCN in these complexes may give rise to doublet nature of the bands.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Solvents were purified and dried before use by usual procedures. The elemental analyses were carried out at the R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow. The electronic spectra (methanol) were recorded on a Hitachi 200-20 spectrophotometer and IR spectra (KBr/nujol/HCB) on a Perkin-Elmer 1330 spectrophotometer. Molar conductance was measured using an Elico conductivity bridge. The magnetic susceptibility was determined by the Gouy method. Molecular weight was determined by Rast's method. 1,3-Diaminopropane-2-ol (Aldrich) was used as such. Schiff bases *N,N'*-(2-hydroxy)propylenebis(2-imino-3-oximino)butane (H_2L^1), *N,N'*-(2-hydroxy)propylenebis(acetylacetonimine) (H_2L^2) and *N,N'*-propylenebis(benzaldimine) (L^3) were prepared by reported methods¹¹, involving the condensation of 1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol with diacetylmonoxime and acetylacetone and 1,3-diaminopropane with benzaldehyde, respectively.

$[Cr(L^1)(Py)Cl].2H_2O$ (1) : Schiff base H_2L^1 (0.001 mol) and $CrCl_3.6H_2O$ (0.001 mol) were taken in boiling pyridine (50 cm³) immediately followed by the addition of zinc dust (in excess). The mixture was refluxed for 2 h and then filtered. The filtrate, on concentration and on addition of few drops of water, yielded a brown solid, which was washed with cold methanol-water mixture and dried *in vacuo* over fused $CaCl_2$ (yield ~70%).

$[Cr(L^2)(Py)Cl].2H_2O$ (2) : Similar reaction of $CrCl_3.6H_2O$ with H_2L^2 gave this yellowish brown compound in 75% yield.

$[Cr(L^3)_2(Py)Cl](ClO_4)_2$ (3) : The reaction of L^3 and $CrCl_3.6H_2O$ in pyridine (as above) in presence of zinc dust yielded a brown solution, which on concentration and treating with the stoichiometric amount of $Na[ClO_4]$ solution afforded a brown solid on standing, which was crystallized from aqueous ethanol (yield ~50%).

$[Cr(L^3)_2(bipy)](ClO_4)_3$ (4) : An equimolar mixture of $[Cr(L^3)_2(Py)Cl](ClO_4)_2$ (3) and dipyridine (dipy) was refluxed (1 h) in methanol on a water-bath. The resulting brown solution was filtered, the filtrate treated with sodium perchlorate (saturated aqueous solution) and the solid compound was crystallized from aqueous methanol (yield ~60%).

$[Cr(L^1)(NH_3)_2]SCN$ (5), $[Cr(L^2)(NH_3)_2]SCN$ (6) and $[Cr(L^3)_2(NCS)(NH_3)](SCN)_2$ (7) : These reddish brown compounds were obtained by the reactions of equimolar

quantities of H_2L^1 , H_2L^2 and L^3 with Reinecke salt, $NH_4[(Cr(NCS)_4(NH_3)_2].H_2O$ (0.001 mol) in ethanol (70 cm³) under reflux (2 h) in about 60% yield.

$[Cr(HL^1)(NCS)_2]$ (8), $[Cr(HL^2)(NCS)_2]$ (9) and $[Cr(L^3)_2(NCS)_2]SCN$ (10) : An ethanolic solution (50 cm³) of Schiff base H_2L^1 , H_2L^2 or L^3 (0.005 mol) was added to a hot ethanolic solution (30 cm³) of $K_3[Cr(SCN)_6].4H_2O$ (0.005 mol) followed by reflux (2 h). The clear brown filtrate on concentration and cooling afforded these brown compounds (yields ~65%).

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References

1. K. Dey, R. Bhowmick, S. K. Nag, K. Chakraborty and S. Biswas, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1999, **76**, 427, and references cited therein.
2. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
3. P. Coggon, A. T. McPhail, F. E. Mabbs, A. Richards and A. S. Thornby, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 3296; B. N. Figgis and J. Lewis, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", eds. J. Lewis and H. G. Wilkins, Interscience, New York, 1960; S. Yamada and K. Iwasaki, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1971, **5**, 3; M. S. O'Connor and B. O. West, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1968, **21**, 369.
4. S. Yamada and S. K. Yamanouchi, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1972, **45**, 2140.
5. K. Dey, R. L. De and K. C. Roy, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 864.
6. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970.
7. N. Nohayama, S. Tomit and K. Yamasaki, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1975, **10**, 33; D. K. Rastogi, S. K. Dua and S. K. Sahni, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1980, **42**, 323.
8. M. M. Mostafa, K. M. Ibrahim and M. N. H. Moussa, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1984, **9**, 243.
9. K. Dey, K. K. Nandi and G. B. Kauffman, *Polyhedron*, 1994, **13**, 2049.
10. K. Dey, D. Bandyopadhyay and J. K. Bhar, *Synth. React. Metal-Organ. Chem.*, 1986, **18**, 849, and references cited therein.
11. K. Dey, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1970, **376**, 209; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 641; K. Dey, S. C. Sadhu, N. B. Chawdhury and K. K. Chatterjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 973.
12. L. H. Jone, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1954, **22**, 1135; 1959, **27**, 665; J. Lewis, R. S. Nyholm and P. W. Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 4590.